

CHEMOTHERAPY OF MALARIA. 6-METHOXYQUINOLINE-8-HYDRAZINE AND SYNTHESIS OF SOME HETERO-CYCLIC COMPOUNDS FROM IT.*

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Starting from 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine a few heterocyclic compounds *e.g.*, thiazole, benzopyrrole, pyrazolone and a pyrrole have been prepared. Some of the compounds have been found to be ineffective against avian malaria.

Plasmoquine, synthesised by Schulemann *et al* (*Klin. Woch.*, 1932, 9, 381), is a 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline derivative. Several derivatives of this substance have been made with different side-chains to find out a more suitable antimalarial drug with less toxicity. In this paper 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline has been converted into 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine by following the method described by Dufton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 757; 1892, 61, 785). This quinolyldiazine is then condensed with various ketones, thiocyanate, etc. giving a thiazole, benzopyrrole, pyrazolone and a pyrrole derivative. Thus by the interaction of 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine with potassium thiocyanate 6-methoxyquinoline-8-thiosemicarbazide is obtained which after condensation with *o*-bromo-acetophenone gives 2-(6'-methoxy-8'-hydrazinoquinolyl)-4-phenylthiazole (I, R= methoxy quinolyl. *cf.* Bose and Nandi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 733). The condensation with cyclohexanone and subsequent treatment with dilute sulphuric acid gives 6'-methoxyquinolino-(7': 8': 2 : 3)-tetrahydrobenzopyrrole (II) (Borsche, Witte and Bothe, *Annalen*, 1908, 369, 49). Similarly the condensation product with ethyl acetoacetate is (*cf.* Knorr, *Annalen*, 1887, 238, 147) 1-[8'-(6'-methoxyquinolyl)]-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (III). A pyrrole synthesis has been effected by condensing the quinolyldiazine with pyruvic acid and the product on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid gives 6'-methoxyquinolino-(7': 8': 2 : 3)-pyrrole-5-carboxylic acid (IV) with remarkable ease (Dufton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 786). The quinolyldiazine has also been condensed with potassium cyanate and *dl*-arabinose to make respectively 6-methoxyquinoline-8-semicarbazide and 6-methoxy-8-quinolyldiazine of arabinose.

Some of these compounds have been tested against avian malaria without any effect. Only 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine retains some

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activity against paramaecia which is, however, decidedly weaker than 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline.

R = methoxyquinolyl,

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine.—6-Methoxy-8-aminoquinoline (20 g.) in hydrochloric acid (100 c.c., 22%) was diazotised at 0° with sodium nitrite (9.5 g.). The diazotised solution was quickly filtered and left at 0°. The stannous chloride of the hydrazine was at once precipitated when 75 g. of stannous chloride in hydrochloric acid were added. After keeping for an hour in the cold the precipitate was collected and dissolved in sufficient boiling water and the tin precipitated by hydrogen sulphide. The filtrate was evaporated down considerably and the free hydrazine was precipitated by sodium hydroxide. It crystallised from hot water in fine, long slender needles, m.p. 67°. (Found: C, 63.11; H, 5.93; N, 22.40. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_3$ requires C, 63.48; H, 5.82; N, 22.22 per cent).

1-(6'-Methoxyquinoline)-8'-thiosemicarbazide.—Equimolecular proportions of 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine and potassium thiocyanate were dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and water respectively. After

the addition of thiocyanate solution to the former, the mixture was boiled for 15 minutes. After cooling, the solution was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and the thiosemicarbazide collected and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 259-61° (Found: N, 22.51; S, 12.67. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_4S$ requires N, 22.58; S, 12.90 per cent).

2- (6'-Methoxy-8'-hydrazinoquinolyl) . 4-phenylthiazole. — 6-Methoxyquinoline-8-thiosemicarbazide (6 g.) and ω -bromoacetophenone (5 g.) were dissolved in alcohol and heated under reflux on the water-bath for about 1½ hours. The solution was then made strongly alkaline with sodium hydroxide and the precipitated thiazole collected, washed well with water, and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 121-24°, yield 20%. (Found: N, 16.31; S, 8.88. $C_{16}H_{16}ON_4S$ requires N, 16.09; S, 9.19 per cent).

6-Methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazone of cyclohexanone. — 6-Methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine (4 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and diluted to 30 c.c., was mixed with a solution of cyclohexanone (2 g.), dissolved in 20 c.c. of alcohol, when an oil separated. After warming on the water-bath for a few minutes it was allowed to stand, when the oil solidified on scratching. The product crystallises from dilute alcohol in shining pale green needles, m.p. 91°. (Found: N, 15.76. $C_{16}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 15.61 per cent).

6-Methoxyquinolino-(7':8':2:3)-tetrahydrobenzopyrrole. — The 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazone of cyclohexanone passes easily into the benzopyrrole on heating in dilute sulphuric acid for a few minutes on the water-bath. The yellow sulphate of the benzopyrrole was suspended in water, made alkaline and extracted with ether in which it dissolves on prolonged shaking. On slow evaporation of ether the benzopyrrole crystallised out in colourless plates, m.p. 181-82°. The sulphate of the benzopyrrole is fluorescent in alcohol and chloroform. The hydrochloride of the base was obtained as yellow crystals by passing hydrogen chloride in ethereal solution, m.p. 256-59°. (Found: C 75.97; H 6.25; N, 11.28. $C_{16}H_{16}ON_2$ requires C, 76.19; H, 6.34; N, 11.11 per cent).

1- [8'-(6'-Methoxyquinolyl)]-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone. — A mixture of 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine (3.2 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (2.8 g.) was heated on the steam-bath for 2-3 hours. The deep coloured product solidified on cooling and scratching and was crystallised from ligroin (b.p. 80-110°), m.p. 72°. This crystallised product was then heated on the steam-bath for nearly 8 hours when it was converted into the pyrazolone. The pyrazolone also crystallised from ligroin, m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 65.72; H, 4.68; N, 16.39. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires C, 66.14; H, 4.72; N, 16.53 per cent).

6'-Methoxyquinoline- (7' : 8' : 2 : 3) -pyrrole-5-carboxylic Acid.—On adding pyruvic acid to a concentrated aqueous solution of 6-methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine hydrochloride in molecular proportions, the mixture became almost solid due to the separation of the hydrochloride of the pyruvic acid hydrazone. This substance was crystallised from water. The pyrrole condensation takes place with remarkable ease when the pyruvic acid quinolyldhydrazone was boiled for about an hour with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The liquid darkened and became filled with yellow crystals of the hydrochloride of the pyrrole acid. The free acid was precipitated by making the aqueous solution of the hydrochloride neutral to litmus or by diluting the aqueous solution considerably. It was then crystallised by dissolving in water with a little ammonia and allowing to evaporate in a dish on the water-bath. As the ammonia was driven off, the acid crystallised in beautiful yellow needles. m.p. 197-98°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol. (Found: C 64.07; H, 4.32; N, 11.44. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires C, 64.46; H, 4.13; N, 11.57 per cent).

1- (*6'-Methoxyquinoline*)-8'-semicarbazide (*cf.* Dufton, *loc. cit.*).—The precipitate, as obtained following Dufton, was dissolved in water and the solution made alkaline. The free semicarbazide was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 236-39° (softening from 225°). (Found: N, 23.95. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_4$ requires N, 24.13 per cent).

6-Methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazone of Arabinose.—6-Methoxyquinoline-8-hydrazine (0.5 g.), dissolved in dilute acetic acid (5 c.c.), was mixed with an aqueous solution of arabinose (0.45 g.) and the mixture warmed on the water-bath for a few minutes. The hydrazone separated on scratching and was crystallised from water in pale green needles, m.p. 140°. (Found: N, 12.87. $C_{13}H_{19}O_5N_3$ requires N, 13.08 per cent).

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